

THE PROBLEM OF LIMITED RESOURCES IN THE ECONOMY.

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Annotation:

In recent years, along with cotton cultivation, the area of grain, fodder, vegetables and other crops has been increasing in the cotton-growing zones of our country. Although these works were carried out mainly as a result of the development of new lands, now it is necessary to meet the demand for agricultural products through more efficient use of existing irrigated lands.

Key words: ensuring food security, organizational and economic mechanisms, agricultural and livestock products, planting fruitful fruit and vegetable crops.

Аннотация:

В последние годы, помимо возделывания хлопчатника, в хлопководческих зонах нашей страны увеличиваются площади зерновых, кормовых, овощных и других культур. Хотя раньше эти работы проводились в основном за счет освоения новых земель, теперь необходимо обеспечить потребность в сельскохозяйственной продукции за счет более эффективного использования имеющихся орошаемых земель.

Ключевые слова: обеспечение продовольственной безопасности, организационно-экономические механизмы, продукция сельского хозяйства и животноводства, посадка урожайных плодовоовощных культур.

It is known that the role of farmers and landowners in ensuring the country's food security is becoming incomparable and will remain so in the near future. However, studies show that the existing potential in agriculture is currently underutilized. There are a number of objective and subjective reasons for this, one of the most important of which is the lack of improvement of the necessary organizational and economic mechanisms for the development of farms.

It is known that the issue of limited resources in the economy primarily concerns land resources. Therefore, it is an important and urgent issue to find ways to effectively use the existing land areas. Therefore, increasing the number of farms specializing in non-traditional farming and animal husbandry products,

such as floriculture and medicinal plant cultivation, using foreign experience, will create an opportunity to increase the competitiveness of the sector.

One of the positive things being done in terms of involving the population in entrepreneurship and improving the standard of living was the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4231 on March 7, 2019. This decision is "On additional measures to involve the population in entrepreneurship in the regions and to develop family entrepreneurship" and was adopted in order to increase the source of income of the population of the regions by engaging in certain labor activities. In this way, increasing the participation of the population, primarily needy families, in the process of growing and processing products, increasing the material interest, based on the study of foreign experience in the production of agricultural products, widely used in local conditions, planting fruitful fruit and vegetable crops, breeding purebred livestock, storing finished products and issues such as paying attention to the recycling process have been taken out.

At the moment, the economically stable development of farms is mainly caused by factors such as the lack of material and technical support of farms, in particular, the lack of necessary equipment, the lack of cooperative relations with other economic entities, and the lack of a system for purchasing cultivated products.

One of the important factors that hinders the sustainable development of agricultural activities is the fact that the integration of peasant farms with other branches of agriculture is not at the required level. 14.03 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The adoption of Resolution No. 4239 of the People's Republic of Azerbaijan in 2019 was a milestone. This Resolution is "On measures for the development of agricultural cooperation in the field of fruit and vegetable production" and is a complex project aimed at improving the fruit and vegetable industry in our country, significantly increasing the arable land of fruit and vegetable crops, storage and processing capacities, and actively attracting funds from international financial institutions. adopted in order to further accelerate the measures. According to this decision, the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Economy and Industry, together with the Council of Farmers, Peasants and Homestead Land Owners of Uzbekistan will submit proposals for the formation of the Institute of Agricultural Associations, that is, this process will be continued until December 2020. The main tasks of agricultural associations were determined. In particular, comprehensive tasks such as production, storage, processing of fruit and vegetable products,

provision of modern technical equipment, marketing of domestic and foreign markets, export, and provision of guaranteed market relations support the activities of farmers, peasant farms and landowners. .

From this point of view, it is important to establish strong integrated relations between farms and other enterprises, to provide necessary resources in this process, and to achieve sales of the grown products under favorable conditions for farmers.

It should be noted that today there is no well-regulated, convenient supply system for farmers. The provision of necessary resources to farms is mainly carried out by private individuals. This leads to the limitation of their access to quality resources.

In our opinion, one of the main ways to solve the above-mentioned problems is the establishment of a separate "supply-service" system, which deals with the provision of necessary resources to farms in the country and region. This system, whether organized as a separate infrastructure object or as a community-based link, was recognized in the questionnaires as a solution to the problem of the survey participants.

In recent years, along with cotton cultivation, the area of grain, fodder, vegetables and other crops has been increasing in the cotton-growing zones of our country. Although these works were carried out mainly as a result of the development of new lands, now it is necessary to meet the demand for agricultural products through more efficient use of existing irrigated lands. Also, legal documents were signed, which envisage the cultivation of medicinal plants, the raw materials necessary for the pharmaceutical industry, in the use of land. One of the most important issues is the purposeful search for medicinal plants found in nature, their cultivation, adaptation to different soil and climate conditions, cultivation under special agrotechnological conditions. Our government paid attention to this issue, and in accordance with the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 8 specialized farms engaged in the cultivation of medicinal plants were established. In addition to these, cultivation is being carried out in the Republican Forest Farms, some farmers, peasant farms and homestead land owners.

Most of the products grown by farmers are sold as they are, unprocessed, and this causes them to work the same way, and their sources of income do not increase. In order to increase the income sources of farmers in the future, we believe that it is appropriate to implement the following measures.

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